
SEROPREVALENCE OF VARICELLA-ZOSTER VIRUS INFECTION AMONG
PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN IN KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

Yusuf, H. and Ella, E.E.

Dept. of Microbiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Centre for Biotechnology Research and Training, A. B. U.,
Zaria.

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out in the three geopolitical zone of Kaduna State, comprising Makarfi (Kaduna North) Kagarko (Kaduna South) and Igabi (Kaduna Central). A total of 353 serum samples collected, were tested VZV Immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies using a commercial IgG enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The overall seroprevalence rate was 66.3%. Seroprevalence was 51.4% in the age group of 4-6 years, 64.7% in 7-9 years, 68.4 % in 10-12 years and 70.0 % in 13-15 years. The seroprevalence rate of VZV increased with age. There was significant relation between the presence of VZV antibodies and age ($P = 0.000$). There was no significance difference between the presence of VZV antibodies and sex ($P = 0.48$). This data show that the younger age group could be considered as a target group for prevention programs against VZV infection.

KEYWORDS: Seroprevalence; Varicella Zoster Virus, Antibody.

INTRODUCTION

Varicella Zoster Virus (VZV) is a human alphaherpesvirus that causes varicella (chickenpox) as the primary infection and establishes latency in sensory ganglia. VZV reactivation results in herpes zoster (shingles). During the course of varicella and zoster, VZV infects differentiated human cells that exist within unique tissue microenvironments in humans. The tropism of VZV for skin is the most obvious clinical manifestation of VZV infection, producing the vesicular cutaneous lesions that are associated with varicella and zoster (Arvin, 2001a). The clinical pattern of primary VZV infection is highly predictable, beginning with an incubation period of 10–21 days following a close exposure of a susceptible individual to another person with varicella or in some cases, herpes zoster (Arvin, 2001b). Varicella often begins with a prodrome of fever, malaise, headache and abdominal pain. These initial symptoms last about 24–48 h before skin vesicles are noted and are more common in older children and adults (Asano *et al.*, 1990; Koropchak *et al.*, 1991).

Worldwide, varicella is an endemic disease that exhibits a marked seasonal pattern in temperate climates and most temperate climates where this has been studied (Bramley and Jones 2000; Seward *et al.*, 2002; Tobias *et al.*, 1998). The exception is Singapore where seasonality has not been described from surveillance data (Ooi *et al.*, 1992). In temperate and tropical climates, the peak disease incidence is most commonly reported in the cooler, drier months during winter or spring. Periodicity with inter epidemic cycles of 2–5 years is described from many countries (Seward *et al.*, 2000; Tobias *et al.*, 1998). In temperate climates, greater than 90% of adolescents or young adults are VZV seropositive while in tropical climates, serological studies show higher susceptibility among adults reflecting a higher mean age of infection. Seroprevalence among adolescents or young adults has varied widely from less than 20% in St. Lucia (an island community in the West Indies) to greater than 90% in tropical areas in Brazil and urban Calcutta, India (Lee, 1998; Ooi *et al.*, 1992; Reis *et al.*, 2003). Because of its high incidence in young children, varicella is one of the most common communicable diseases in child care centers and attendance in child care or preschools provides the opportunity for exposure to the varicella zoster virus (VZV) at younger ages. The objective of this study was to provide seroprevalence studies of the varicella zoster virus in among children in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was carried out in Kaduna State, comprising of 23 Local Government areas. Three (3) Local governments were randomly selected for the study from each senatorial district and these include Makarfi (Kaduna North) with 11 districts, Kagarko (Kaduna South) with 11 districts and Igabi (Kaduna Central) with 10 districts.

Study Design

This study is a cross-sectional study to determine the prevalence of serum IgG against VZV infection among 353 primary school children between ages of 4-15 years in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Information on the children was obtained through questionnaires. By using the sampling frame of primary schools in the various districts of each local government, one school was randomly picked to represent each district in the local government areas. Questionnaires were given to each pupil picked; a written letter seeking the consent of the subject's parent was also forwarded. Those that consented to the request returned the forms with their demographic data filled in.

Sample collection and analysis

Using a sterile disposable syringe, five milliliters (5ml) of venous blood was drawn from children. The blood samples were centrifuged at 1500 rpm for two minutes; sera were separated and stored at -20°C until tested. The sera were tested for the presence of VZV IgG antibodies using a commercial IgG enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) Kit manufactured by DIAGNOSTIC AUTOMATION, INC. USA. This ELISA uses cell-culture-derived VZV antigens for the detection of anti-VZV IgG antibodies in serum. The absorbance was read at 450 nm using an ELISA micro titer plate reader (Sigma Diagnostic). The presence or absence of anti-VZV-specific IgG antibodies in the test samples was calculated according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were obtained by comparing the antibody titers with the cut off values of the positive and negative controls.

Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed using SPSS statistical package version 13 for windows. The chi-square test of association was used to determine differences in the seroprevalence rates in male and female pupils, and to determine the rise in VZV IgG seroprevalence with age.

RESULTS

A total of 353 serum samples collected, were tested VZV IgG antibodies. The overall seroprevalence rate was 66.3%. Seroprevalence was 51.4% in the age group of 4-6 years, 64.7% in 7-9 years, 68.4 % in 10-12 years and 70.0 % in 13-15 years.

Table 1: Distribution of VZV IgG antibody in relation to age

Age group (yrs)	No of samples	No Positive	% Positive
4 – 6	37	19	51.4
7 – 9	85	55	64.7
10 – 12	114	78	68.4
13 – 15	117	82	70

$X^2 = 9.02$, ($P = 0.000$)

Chi-square analysis indicated association ($P=0.000$) between the ages and VZV IgG antibody prevalence.

Table 2: Distribution of VZV IgG antibody in relation to sex

Sex	No of Samples tested	No Positive	% Positive
Male	184	126	68.4
Female	169	108	63.9
Total	353	234	66.3

$X^2 = 0.48$, ($P > 0.05$)

Chi-square analysis indicated no association ($P > 0.05$) between the sexes and VZV IgG antibody prevalence.

The seroprevalence rate of VZV increased with age (Table 1). There was significant relation between the presence of VZV antibodies and age ($P = 0.000$). There was no significance difference between the presence of VZV antibodies and sex ($P = 0.48$), (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

Our results revealed that prevalence of antibodies to varicella increase significantly throughout childhood. The seroprevalence of varicella zoster has been known to increase with age. The older children often go to schools or find themselves in communities often crowded, which brings them in contact with the virus and subsequent development of antibodies. Varicella is generally community acquired, and the rate of contacting it is increased by factors that support crowding and close contact interaction such as public schools. The percentage of cases among young adults may be a cause for alarm since the clinical course of varicella is generally more serious in adults and the incidence of complications is higher. The rise in seroprevalence to over 65% with age has been widely reported in several tropical countries such as the United Arab Emirate, (Uduman *et al*, 2001) and India, (Lokeshwar *et al*, 2000) , while 41% was reported by some investigators in Singapore,(Ooi *et al*, 1992). Possession of protective antibodies to varicella zoster confers immunity in adult life. However, it is also an indication of the endemic nature of this viral infection as there is no routine vaccine policy for it in Nigeria. Immunity is often developed in the individuals after the first episode of the infection and subsequent exposure to the viral agent. Some reports exist of individuals within the adolescence age that lack protective IgG to varicella zoster (Migasena *et al*, 1997).

The studies in many temperate countries reported near universal seropositivity by early adolescence. Swiss and American studies have reported that over 90% of individuals in Europe and the United States acquire immunity before adolescence (Muench, *et al* 1986; Wharton, 1996). (Fairley and Miller, 1996) there was 80% seropositivity by the age of 7 years in Spanish children (Eguliz *et al*, 1987) and 83% seroconversion by the age of 9 years in Japanese children (Taylor-Wiedeman *et al*, 1989).

In our studies, there was no association between seroprevalence with sex showing that sex differences do not play any significant role in the acquisition of the infection.

The virus thrive best in temperate climate and this reflected in the near 100% seroprevalence recorded in these countries. The low seroprevalence in tropical region could therefore be attributed to the fact that high ambient temperature and humidity in the tropics decreases VZV transmission by inactivating the virus in the cutaneous lesions. It is also possible that because of high prevalence of certain other childhood viruses in tropical countries, there is interference with the transmission of varicella zoster and the age of varicella infection is postponed. This view was also expressed by Wilkins *et al*, (1998). The tropical countries should therefore consider the possibility of childhood vaccination with varicella zoster to confer immunity and possible improve of the seroprevalence to the virus. Since the majority of VZV infections occur during the early childhood, the best option to reduce the circulation of wild type VZV in the population would be the immunization of young children. These data are also fundamental for evaluating the suitability of establishing mass varicella vaccination programs. Mass vaccination against VZV should be introduced only if very high coverage can be assured. The impact that a mass vaccination program among children 12-18 months of age could have on the epidemiological trend of the infection must be carefully considered.

CONCLUSION

The finding of this study showed that VZV seroprevalence increased with age in the population studied to a level of 70% in adolescence age. Significant proportions of adolescence are still susceptible to varicella infection. There was no association between seroprevalence of VZV with sex of the subjects studied.

REFERENCE

- Arvin, A. M. (2001a). Varicella-zoster virus. 4th edn. In *Fields Virology*, D. M. Knipe, and P. M. Howley, eds., Vol. 2, Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven. pp. 2731–2768.
- Arvin, A. M. (2001b). Varicella-zoster virus: molecular virology and virus–host interactions. *Curr. Opin. Microbiol.*, 4(4): 442–449.

Asano, Y., Itakura, N., Kajita, Y. *et al.* (1990). Severity of viremia and clinical findings in children with varicella. *J. Infect. Dis.*, 161(6): 1095–1098.

Bramley, J. C. and Jones, I. G. (2000). Epidemiology of chickenpox in Scotland: 1981 to 1998. *Commun. Dis. Public Health*, 3: 82–87.

Eguliz, G.C., Trallero, E.P., Garcia-Rinsing, J.M. (1987). Seroepidemiology of varicella zoster in children in Spain. *J Infect Dis* ; 156(2):847-851.

Fairley, C.K. and Miller, E. (1996). Varicella-zoster virus epidemiology--a changing scene? *J Infect Dis*; 174 (Suppl 3):314-9.

Koropchak, C. M., Graham, G., Palmer, J. *et al.* (1991). Investigation of varicella-zoster virus infection by polymerase chain reaction in the immunocompetent host with acute varicella. *J. Infect. Dis.*, 163: 1016–1022.

Lee, B. W. (1998). Review of varicella zoster seroepidemiology in India and Southeast Asia. *Trop. Med. Int. Health*, 3(11): 886–890.

Lokeshwar, M.R., Agrawal, A., Subbarao, S.D., Chakraborty, M.S., Ram-Prasad, A.V., Weil, J., *et al.* (2000). Age related seroprevalence of antibodies to varicella in India. *Indian Pediatr*; 37(7):714-9.

Migasena, S., Simasthien, S., Desakorn, V., Phonrat, B., Suntharasamai, P., Pitisuttitham, P., *et al.* (1997). Seroprevalence of varicella zoster virus antibodies in Thailand. *Int. J of Infect Dis.*; 2(1): 26-30.

Muench, R., Nassim, C., Niku, S. and Sullivan-Bolyai, J.Z. (1986). Seroepidemiology of varicella. *J Infect Dis*; 153(1):153-5.

Ooi, P.L., Goh, K.T., Doraisingham, S. and Ling, A.E. (1992). Prevalence of varicella-zoster virus infection in Singapore. Southeast. *Asian J Trop Med Public Health*; 23(1):22-5.

Reis, A. D., Pannuti, C. S., and de Souza, V. A. (2003). Prevalence of varicella-zoster virus antibodies in young adults from different Brazilian climatic regions. *Rev. Soc. Bras. Med. Trop.*, 36(3): 317–320.

Seward, J. F., Watson, B. M., Peterson, C. L. *et al.* (2002). Varicella disease after introduction of varicella vaccine in the United States, 1995–2000. *J. Am. Med. Assoc.*, 287: 606–611.

Taylor-Wiedeman J, Yamashita K, Miyamura K, Yamazaki S. (1989). Varicella-zoster virus prevalence in Japan: no significant change in a decade. *Jpn J Med Sci Biol*; 42(1):1-11.

Tobias, M., Reid, S., Lennon, D. *et al.* (1998). Chickenpox immunization in New Zealand. *NZ Med. J.*, 111: 274–281.

Uduman, S.A., Tahira, A.M., Al-Wash, R., Usmani, M.A. and Bener, A. (2001). Varicella susceptibility among children and healthy adults in the United Arab Emirates. *East Mediterr. Health J* ; 7(4-5):604-8.

Wharton, M. (1996). The epidemiology of varicella zoster virus infections. *Infect Dis Clin North Ame*; 10(3):571-81.

Wilkins, E.G., Leen, C.L.S., Mc-Kendrick, M.W. and Carrington, D. (1998) Management of chickenpox in the adult. *J of Infect Dis*; 36(Suppl 1):49-58.

Yusuf, H. and Ella, E.E: Continental J. Microbiology 5: 1 - 5, 2011

Received for Publication: 03/02/11

Accepted for Publication: 15/03/11

Corresponding Author

Yusuf, H.

Dept. of Microbiology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Email: yuzab1990@yahoo.com